

Supplementary Information

Factors influencing the accuracy and precision
in dating single gene trees

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Supplementary information S1 21 species Primate tree with median branch lengths.

Branch lengths are the median number of substitutions per nucleotide from the 5204 gene trees, obtained from the Beast clock model fit.

Supplementary information S2 Complete list of the 56 input features for the regression.

To obtain the final selection of features, the following removal criteria were checked in order:

1. constant features;
2. collinear features upon PCA inspection;
3. features which identify aberrant gene trees (outliers), alongside their corresponding aberrant trees;
4. features not retained by the Lasso fit, or with a coefficient strictly less than 0.01.

Retained variables are highlighted in light green.

Variable	Description	Removal
Input tree features (reconciled trees)		
aberrant_dists	Number of branches with length > 10000	(1)
rebuilt_topo	Tree topology was forced to fit the species tree	(4)
unlike_clock	Root-to-tip length deviation in the Ensembl tree	(4)
bootstrap_min	Minimum node bootstrap value (Ensembl)	(4)
bootstrap_mean	Mean node bootstrap value (Ensembl)	(2)
RF	Gene tree discordance with the species tree (Robinson-Foulds)	(4)
Alignment features (based on ingroup sequences only)		
ingroup_glob_len	Alignment length	(4)
ingroup_mean_GC	Average GC-content of ingroup sequences	(4)
ingroup_mean_N	Average proportion of ambiguous nucleotides per sequence	(4)
ingroup_mean_gaps	Average proportion of gaps per sequence	(4)
ingroup_mean_CpG	Average proportion of CpG dinucleotides per sequence	(2)
ingroup_std_len	Standard deviation of sequence lengths	(4)
ingroup_std_GC	Std. dev. of the GC-content of ingroup sequences	(2)
ingroup_std_N	Std. dev. of the proportion of ambiguous nucleotides per sequence	(2)
ingroup_std_gaps	Std. dev. of the proportion of gaps per sequence	(2)
ingroup_std_CpG	Std. dev. of the proportion of CpG per sequence	(2)
ingroup_nucl_entropy_mean	Mean entropy score across aligned nucleotides	(2)
ingroup_nucl_entropy_median	Median entropy score across aligned nucleotides	(4)
ingroup_nucl_entropy_std	Std. dev. of the entropy score across aligned nucleotides	(2)
ingroup_nucl_parsimony_mean	Mean parsimony score across aligned nucleotides	(2)
ingroup_nucl_parsimony_std	Std. dev. of the parsimony score across aligned nucleotides	(4)
ingroup_codon_entropy_mean	Mean entropy score across aligned codons	(2)
ingroup_codon_entropy_median	Median entropy score across aligned codons	(2)
ingroup_codon_entropy_std	Std. dev. of the entropy score across aligned codons	(2)
ingroup_codon_parsimony_mean	Mean parsimony score across aligned codons	(2)
ingroup_codon_parsimony_median	Median parsimony score across aligned codons	(2)
ingroup_codon_parsimony_std	Std. dev. of the parsimony score across aligned codons	(2)
Output from alignment filtering		
prop_splitseq	proportion of non-overlapping sequences	(3)
hmmc_propseqs	Proportion of sequences modified by HmmCleaner	(4)
hmmc_max	Maximum proportion of sequence deleted by HmmCleaner	(4)
Codeml output features		
NsynSites	Amount of synonymous substitutions in the stationary state	(4)
brOmega_mean	Average $\omega = dN/dS$ of branches	(4)
brOmega_std	Standard deviation of $\omega = dN/dS$ of branches	(4)
brOmega_skew	Skew of $\omega = dN/dS$ of branches	(4)
ls	Number of aligned sites	(2)
Beast outputs		
unconverged	Has at least one parameter with ESS < 200	(3)
beast_nsamples	Number of samples in the MCMC chain	(4)
treeL_12_med	Total tree length at codon positions 1,2 (posterior median)	(2)
treeL_3_med	Total tree length at codon positions 3	(2)
gammaShape_12_med	Shape of gamma site rates at codon positions 1,2	(4)
gammaShape_3_med	Shape of gamma site rates at codon position 3	(4)
kappa_12_med	κ at codon positions 1,2	(4)
kappa_3_med	κ at codon position 3	(4)
uclMean_12_med	Beast lognormal clock mean parameter at codon positions 1,2	(2)

uclMean_3_med	Beast lognormal clock mean parameter at codon positions 3	(2)
uclStdev_12_med	Beast lognormal clock standard deviation parameter at codon positions 1,2	(2)
uclStdev_3_med	Beast lognormal clock standard deviation parameter at codon positions 3	(2)
rate_12_mean_med	Branch average of the Beast rate statistic at codon positions 1,2	(2)
rate_12_var_med	Branch variance of the Beast rate statistic at codon positions 1,2	(2)
rate_3_mean_med	Branch average of the Beast rate statistic at codon positions 3	(2)
rate_3_var_med	Branch variance of the Beast rate statistic at codon positions 3	(2)

Rate features

beastmedian_rate	Branch-average of the Beast rate statistic, in subst/codon/My (posterior median)	
beastclockmedian_rate	Beast lognormal clock mean parameter (posterior median)	(2)
beastmedian_rate_std	Branch heterogeneity of the rate statistic (sum of std. dev. for all codon positions)	
beastclockmedian_rate_std	Branch heterogeneity of the clock rate (sum of the standard deviation of the lognormal clock for all codon positions)	(2)

Supplementary information S3 Alternative regression to the one in the main text. Here the only feature for measuring across-branch rate variation is the root-to-tip deviation. The regularization parameter is also $\alpha = 0.02$.

Supplementary information S4 Enriched human gene annotations from the set with lowest predicted dispersion. Significance threshold 0.05, multiple testing correction by g:SCS (defaults).

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ID	Source	Term ID	Term Name	Padj (query_1)
1	GO:MF	GO:0005524	ATP binding	2.065×10^{-3}
2	GO:BP	GO:0071840	cellular component organization or biogene...	2.642×10^{-8}
3	GO:CC	GO:0043228	non-membrane-bounded organelle	6.477×10^{-5}
4	GO:CC	GO:0005604	basement membrane	1.475×10^{-3}
5	HP	HP:0000707	Abnormality of the nervous system	1.954×10^{-4}
6	HP	HP:0000478	Abnormality of the eye	6.484×10^{-4}
7	HP	HP:0001321	Cerebellar hypoplasia	5.342×10^{-4}
8	HP	HP:0004375	Neoplasm of the nervous system	3.166×10^{-4}
9	HP	HP:0012823	Clinical modifier	4.589×10^{-4}
10	HP	HP:0031703	Abnormal ear morphology	7.519×10^{-4}
11	HP	HP:0100022	Abnormality of movement	6.059×10^{-4}
12	HP	HP:0012373	Abnormal eye physiology	1.719×10^{-3}
13	HP	HP:0007360	Aplasia/Hypoplasia of the cerebellum	1.221×10^{-3}

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 organism hsapiens

g:Profiler

Supplementary information S5

Enriched human gene annotations from the set of genes with longest alignment. Same parameters as above (defaults).

ID	Source	Term ID	Term Name	Padj (query_1)
1	GO:MF	GO:0140657	ATP-dependent activity	1.052×10 ⁻¹⁰
2	GO:MF	GO:0005524	ATP binding	1.141×10 ⁻⁷
3	GO:MF	GO:0005198	structural molecule activity	1.119×10 ⁻⁵
4	GO:MF	GO:0008017	microtubule binding	2.924×10 ⁻⁵
5	GO:MF	GO:0030695	GTPase regulator activity	7.597×10 ⁻⁵
6	GO:MF	GO:0044877	protein-containing complex binding	7.736×10 ⁻⁴
7	GO:MF	GO:0003774	cytoskeletal motor activity	2.043×10 ⁻²
8	GO:MF	GO:0008331	high voltage-gated calcium channel activity	3.348×10 ⁻²
9	GO:BP	GO:0016043	cellular component organization	1.926×10 ⁻²²
10	GO:BP	GO:0051056	regulation of small GTPase mediated signal ...	9.359×10 ⁻⁶
11	GO:CC	GO:0043232	intracellular non-membrane-bounded organ...	7.269×10 ⁻¹²
12	GO:CC	GO:0099080	supramolecular complex	6.406×10 ⁻⁷
13	GO:CC	GO:0005604	basement membrane	3.271×10 ⁻⁵
14	GO:CC	GO:0030054	cell junction	4.296×10 ⁻³
15	HP	HP:0000366	Abnormality of the nose	2.663×10 ⁻¹⁶
16	HP	HP:0000290	Abnormality of the forehead	5.302×10 ⁻¹⁶
17	HP	HP:0005105	Abnormal nasal morphology	5.186×10 ⁻¹⁶
18	HP	HP:0002683	Abnormal calvaria morphology	5.518×10 ⁻¹⁵
19	HP	HP:0012373	Abnormal eye physiology	1.294×10 ⁻¹⁴
20	HP	HP:0100886	Abnormality of globe location	1.052×10 ⁻¹⁴
21	HP	HP:0000478	Abnormality of the eye	1.264×10 ⁻¹⁴

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 organism hsapiens

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Supplementary information S6 Observed distributions of the simulated parameters in the Primates gene trees.

Supplementary information S7 Sampling from the prior of the Beast model. The underlying tree (black lines) show the dates from TimeTree.

Supplementary information S8 Species and gene trees preprocessing

The tree of the 99 species from Ensembl Compara 93 is based on the NCBI taxonomy and was edited to resolve polytomies based on multiple sources, including a dated phylogeny from TimeTree (data retrieved Jan. 2019; Kumar et al. 2017) and reference literature (Perelman et al. 2011; Mittermeier et al. 2013; Upham et al. 2019).

We first removed species with low genome assembly quality, as quantified by the $N50$ (size of scaffold in number of genes, such that 50% of genes are contained in larger scaffolds) and the $K70$ (number of the longest scaffolds which contain more than 70% of the genes). Species with $N50 < 30$ genes and $K70 > 400$ scaffolds were removed, including 3 primate species out of 24 (*Rhinopithecus bieti*, *Rhinopithecus roxellana*, *Carlito syrichta*) retaining 21 primate species of which 18 Simiiformes.

Our species tree topology was then applied on the downloaded gene trees from Ensembl, requiring that some nodes be edited (automatically; Peres and Roest Crollius 2015). In the original gene tree forest from Ensembl, 729 subtrees supported by aberrant branch lengths (above 10,000 nucleotide substitutions per site) were removed, and 6962 annotated gene splits (one true gene artefactually annotated as two or more genes fragments) were merged.

Supplementary information S9 Program versions.

We ran analyses on an Ubuntu 18.04 operating system.

For statistical analyses we used Python 3.8.10 (Jun 22 2022, 20:18:18)

The following Python packages and versions were last used:

Numpy	1.22.3 (GCC 9.4.0)
Scipy	1.8.0
Pandas	1.4.1
Statsmodels	0.13.2
Scikit-learn	1.0.2
Matplotlib	3.5.3
Seaborn	0.11.2
Biopython	1.79
Ete3	3.1.2
IPython	8.4.0

Supplementary information S10 Beast clock model parameters VS rate summary statistics.

Supplementary information S11 Feature transformations

Decorrelation operators:

- / division;
- subtraction;
- ~ regress and keep the residuals.

	Transform	Decorrelation	Renaming after decorrelation
rebuilt_topo	log10(1 + x)		
unlike_clock	log10		
bootstrap_min	notransform		
bootstrap_mean	notransform		
RF	sqrt		
ingroup_glob_len	log10		
ingroup_mean_GC	notransform		
ingroup_mean_N	log10(1.2321e-05 + x)		
ingroup_mean_gaps	log10(0.00257095 + x)		
ingroup_mean_CpG	log10	/ ingroup_mean_GC ²	CpG_odds
ingroup_std_len	log10(3.04024 + x)		
ingroup_std_GC	log10		
ingroup_std_N	log10(5.08009e-05 + x)		
ingroup_std_gaps	sqrt		
ingroup_std_CpG	log10		
ingroup_nucl_entropy_mean	sqrt		
ingroup_nucl_entropy_median	binarize		
ingroup_nucl_entropy_std	sqrt		
ingroup_nucl_parsimony_mean	log10(0 + x)		
ingroup_nucl_parsimony_std	log10(0 + x)	~ ingroup_nucl_parsimony_mean	Ringroup_nucl_parsimony_std
ingroup_codon_entropy_mean	log10		
ingroup_codon_entropy_median	binarize		
ingroup_codon_entropy_std	sqrt		
ingroup_codon_parsimony_mean	log10		
ingroup_codon_parsimony_median	binarize		
ingroup_codon_parsimony_std	sqrt		
prop_splitseq	binarize		
hmmc_propseqs	notransform		
hmmc_max	log10(0.00676366 + x)		
treeL_12_med	-log10(-x)		
treeL_3_med	-log10(-x)		
gammaShape_12_med	log10		
gammaShape_3_med	log10		
kappa_12_med	log10		
kappa_3_med	log10		
uclMean_12_med	log10		
uclMean_3_med	log10		
uclStdev_12_med	log10		
uclStdev_3_med	log10		
unconverged	binarize		
beast_nsamples	binarize (cutoff 10002)		
rate_12_mean_med	log10		
rate_12_var_med	log10		
rate_3_mean_med	log10		
rate_3_var_med	log10(sqrt(x))		
NsynSites	log10	– ls	RsynSites
brOmega_mean	sqrt		
brOmega_std	sqrt	/ brOmega_mean	RbrOmega_std
brOmega_skew	notransform		
ls	log10		
beastmedian_rate	log10		
beastclockmedian_rate	log10		
beastmedian_rate_std	log10	~ beastmedian_rate	Rbeastmedian_rate_std
beastclockmedian_rate_std	log10		
beastclock_rate_extreme	binarize		
beastclockmedian_rate_extreme	binarize		

Supplementary information S12 Aberrant gene trees (35), removed prior to the regression.

	Threshold	Number of trees
Presence of pairs of sequences without overlap (split)	> 0	16
Presence of an ESS < 200	> 0	13
Beast lognormal clock mean (posterior median)	0.03	1
Beast lognormal clock mean (posterior mean)	0.03	8
Any of the above		35

Supplementary information S13 Detailed outputs and parameters of the regression of per-tree error.

	coef	std err	$P > z $	adj. p-value	[0.025	0.975]	Lasso coef	Simple regression coef	Simple regression R^2	Simple regression p-value	Simple regression adj. p-value
const	-0.0000	0.0120	1.0000	nan	-0.0230	0.0230	0.0000	-0.0000	0.0000	1.0000	nan
ingroup_glob_len	-0.3471	0.0160	0	0.0000	-0.3790	-0.3160	-0.3324	-0.3684	0.1357	0	0
Rbeastmedian_rate_std	0.3014	0.0130	0	0.0000	0.2760	0.3270	0.2814	0.2688	0.0723	0	0
beastmedian_rate	-0.1370	0.0150	0	0.0000	-0.1670	-0.1070	-0.1043	-0.0920	0.0085	0	0
RF	0.0770	0.0150	0	0.0000	0.0470	0.1070	0.0773	0.3165	0.1002	0	0
kappa_3_med	-0.0764	0.0170	0	0.0001	-0.1090	-0.0430	-0.0184	-0.1126	0.0127	0	0
RsynSites	-0.0736	0.0160	0	0.0001	-0.1040	-0.0430	-0.0186	-0.0550	0.0030	0	0.0005
ingroup_std_GC	0.0584	0.0140	0	0.0008	0.0310	0.0860	0.0398	0.1656	0.0274	0	0
unlike_clock	0.0477	0.0130	0	0.0063	0.0220	0.0730	0.0454	0.2278	0.0519	0	0
gammaShape_3_med	-0.0470	0.0150	0	0.0372	-0.0760	-0.0180	-0.0115	-0.0042	0.0000	0.7884	1
kappa_12_med	-0.0427	0.0140	0	0.0645	-0.0700	-0.0150	-0.0505	-0.2255	0.0509	0	0

	Simple regression [0.025	Simple regression 0.975]	VIFs	transform	transformed mean	transformed std	decorr
const	-0.0273	0.0273	1.0000	nan	nan	nan	nan
ingroup_glob_len	-0.3939	-0.3430	1.8128	log10	3.2501	0.2893	
Rbeastmedian_rate_std	0.2400	0.2976	1.2069	log10	-3.3346	0.3854	~ beastmedian_rate
beastmedian_rate	-0.1208	-0.0632	1.4776	log10	-2.6491	0.2009	
RF	0.2888	0.3443	1.6035	sqrt	1.6409	1.0329	
kappa_3_med	-0.1399	-0.0853	1.9512	log10	0.9177	0.1632	
RsynSites	-0.0801	-0.0299	1.7783	log10	2.7077	0.3008	NsynSites - ls
ingroup_std_GC	0.1380	0.1931	1.3596	log10	-2.3732	0.2742	
unlike_clock	0.1996	0.2561	1.1800	log10	-0.7710	0.2383	
gammaShape_3_med	-0.0346	0.0262	1.4072	log10	-0.0600	0.1827	
kappa_12_med	-0.2556	-0.1955	1.2601	log10	0.6129	0.1456	

Column descriptions:

coef coefficient from the multiple regression (OLS fit);

std err standard error of the previous coefficient;

$P > |z|$ p-value of the coefficient being different from zero (yellow background means significant at level 0.05);

adj. p-value p-value adjusted by a Bonferroni correction;

[0.025, 0.975] 95% confidence interval upper/lower limits;

Lasso coef coefficient of the lasso regression used to select features;

Simple regression coef, R^2 , p-value, ... for comparison with the multiple regression, simple regressions (i.e., testing one variable at a time, with intercept) were computed;

VIF Variance Inflation Factor. This metric characterizes the collinearity added by a variable. Values above 10 should be avoided.

transform the function applied to the raw variable prior to regressing;

transformed mean, std mean and standard deviation of the variable post-transform;

decorr how, and against which variable a variable was “decorrelated”. “~” indicates that the residuals from a simple regression were kept.

Supplementary information S14 Observed distribution of κ (transitions/transversions) in the Primates gene trees.

Supplementary information S15 Number of trees having one or more variable with ESS<200

Dataset		Number of trees with ESS<200
Empirical		
	5205 Primates gene trees	13
Simulated (500 replicates each)		
Alignment length	mean rate μ	rate heterogeneity σ/μ
300	40×10^{-4}	1/4
3000	40×10^{-4}	1/4
30000	40×10^{-4}	1/4
3000	5×10^{-4}	1/4
3000	80×10^{-4}	1/4
3000	40×10^{-4}	1/20
3000	40×10^{-4}	1

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